

CURRENT PROBLEMS OF FIELD RESEARCH IN ETHNOGRAPHY

Maksetov Kutlimurat Makset uli

Master's student of Karakalpak State University named after Berdakh, Nukus

Annotation. In this article, we talk about field ethnography and its features. The main principles of the field research methodology are the method of participant observation.

This article discusses some of the problems of working in the field to obtain ethnographic materials. The paper also analyzes field research, which is attractive to those who like to observe people or prefer a free approach to conducting research.

Key words: informants, social problems, ideology, field research methodology, socioanthropology, ethnomethodology.

Field research is the study of people acting in the natural environment of their daily lives. A field researcher ventures into the world of other people to learn " first hand " about how they live, how they talk, behave, what fascinates and disappoints them. It is also a method of study by which researchers try to understand the meaning (meaning) of the observed activity for those who are involved in it " [1, 23 p.].

Field studies of "qualitative" are similar to ethnography, included observation. They have no strict mathematics or complex statistics, no focus on abstract deductive hypotheses. Instead, direct social interaction "face to face" in a natural environment.

Field research is attractive to those who like to observe people or prefer a free approach to conducting research. The scientist communicates directly with and observes the people he studies. By interacting for a number of months or years, he (she) learns a lot about them: their life story, hobbies and interests, habits, hopes, fears and dreams.

When should field research be used? Field research is adequate when the research topic involves the study, understanding or description of a group of interacting people. It can be used when other methods (surveys, experiments) cannot be used, such as in

the study of street gangs. Jack Douglas believes that the bulk of what social scientists want to know can only be obtained by directly involving the researcher in the field [2, 36 p.].

Field researchers study people in a particular place or environment. Field research can also be used to study vague, amorphous social experiences where intensive interviewing and observation is the only way to gain access to the experience. The subject of research can be, for example, the feelings of a person who was attacked, or the personality of a widow whose husband committed suicide [3, 69 p.]. The people we study in the field will be referred to as group members for terminology purposes.

Field research is rooted in travelers' reports of distant wanderings. In the 1200s, travelers and missionaries described foreign cultures and the peoples they met. People read these descriptions to learn more about other cultures. Later, in the 19th century, as trade and empires in Europe expanded rapidly, there were more educated travelers and the number of such communications increased.

Academic fieldwork began in the late 19th century. with the advent of anthropology. Early anthropologists only read the reports of travelers, government - officials, or missionaries; they lacked direct contact with the people they studied. The reports focused on the exotic and were often racist and ethno -centric in content. Travelers rarely spoke the local languages and had to rely on interpreters. In the 1890s European anthropologists began to travel to distant lands to learn about other cultures.

The British socioanthropologist Bronisław Malinowski (1844-1942) was the first researcher to live with a group of people for a long time and write about the collected data. In the 1920s he introduced intensive field work as a new method and substantiated the distinction between the direct observations and statements of the natives and the conclusions of the researcher. He said that social scientists should directly interact with the natives, live among them, study customs, ideas and social processes.

Researchers have also applied field research to study their own societies. The observations of the poor in London by C. Booth and B. Web in the 1890s marked the beginning of surveys and fieldwork that went beyond anthropology. The participant

observation appeared probably in Germany in 1890 г. P. Gore worked as a factory apprentice for three months and took notes every night in order to study factory life. His work influenced university scientists, including Max Weber.

Sociological field research in the United States began to be carried out at the Department of Sociology at the University of Chicago, where the well-known Chicago School of Sociology later took shape. The influence of the Chicago School on fieldwork went through two stages. In the first stage, from the 1910s to the 1930s, the school used a variety of methods based on "case study" or life stories, including direct observation, informal interviews, reading documents, official reports. B 1916 R.E. The park drew up a program of social exploration of the city in Chicago. Influenced by his own previous experience as a reporter, he argued that social scientists should leave libraries and "get their hands dirty" by making direct observations and conversations in the streets, in bars, in the lobbies of luxury hotels. A few early studies formed the basis of the early Chicago School of Sociology as a descriptive study of street life, followed by some analysis.

At the first stage, journalistic and anthropological research models were combined. In the second (from the early 1940s to the 1960s), the Chicago School developed participant observation as a special technique. It applied an extended anthropological model in relation to groups and environments in the society in which the researcher himself lived. Three principles emerged: to study people in their natural environment or situation; study people through direct interaction with them; achieve an understanding of the social world and draw theoretical conclusions about the perspectives of group members.

Theoretical analysis based on the participation of the researcher in the field.

After World War II, ethnologists' fieldwork faced increased competition from questionnaires and quantitative research. From the period after World War II to the 1970s. the proportion of qualitative field research among all social research has declined. However, in the 1970s and 1980s there were some changes that revived them again. First, the fieldwork has borrowed heavily from cognitive psychology, cultural anthropology, folklore, and linguistics. Secondly, the researchers revised the epistemological roots and philosophical premises of social science, which established

this method. Finally, field researchers became more aware of their technique and methods. They wrote about methodology and systematized research technique.

Currently, field researchers have a special set of methodologies. They directly observe and interact with the members of the group in their natural surroundings in order to understand their "inside" perspective. At the same time, they dwell on the activist or social-constructivist perspectives of social life.

Field researchers do not see people as neutral agents through which social forces operate, and social meanings as something abstract. On the contrary, they believe that people create and define the social world through interaction. People's experience is filtered through a subjective sense of reality. It affects how people view events and how they act. Consequently, these researchers are moving away from the positivist emphasis on "objective facts", focusing on everyday (face to face) social processes of negotiation, discussion, in order to construct social meaning.

Ethnologists transfer the social-constructivist perspective to the research process itself. They see research as both a description of the social world and part of it. The presence of the researcher in the field is part of the social environment being created, and cannot simply be a neutral collection of information.

Qualitative field research has been developed in ethnography and ethnomethodology based on a social construction approach. They review the traditional methodology for conducting field research. However, they have not yet become the core of field research, so very little is discussed here.

Ethnography comes from cultural anthropology [5, p.112]. Ethnography is a description of a culture and an understanding of a different way of life from the point of view of an indigenous person. Charles Frank writes: "Culture, the object of our description, comes from the ideas of the indigenous people (natives)" [6, p. 61]. Ethnography allows people to make assumptions - that is, go from what is shown explicitly to what was meant or implied. People discover their culture (what they think, what they think, what they believe) through behavior (eg speech, actions) in specific social contexts. Behaviors do not convey meaning; the meaning is rather implied or revealed by someone. At the center of ethnography is the progression from what is observed to what is really meant.

Ethnographers describe the explicit and implicit cultural knowledge shared by group members. Detailed description and careful analysis help to connect what is described separately.

Anthropologist Clifford Girtz considers an important part of ethnography to be "rich" description - a rich description of features (as opposed to short description, standardization, generalization or variables) [7, p. 55]. A detailed description of a three- minute event can take up many pages. It captures the meaning of what happened and the dramaturgy of events, leaving room for numerous interpretations. Events are placed in context so that the reader of the ethnographic report can come to a conclusion about the cultural significance of what is happening.

Ethnomethodology is a specific approach developed in the 1960s. and having its own unique methodology [8, p. 88]. It combines theory, philosophy and method. Some scholars do not consider it as part of sociology. Mehan and Wood note: "Ethnomethodology is not a set of conclusions, not a method, not a theory, not a worldview ... it is an attempt to discover a level of reality that exists beyond the sociological level ... It differs from sociology in the same way that sociology differs from psychology "[8, p. 69]. A simple definition of ethnomethodology is "the study of knowledge based on common sense". Ethnomethodologists study common sense by observing its development and use in behavior and social interaction in natural settings. Ethnomethodology is a radical or extreme form of field research based on phenomenological philosophy and a social construction approach. It includes specialized, highly detailed analysis of micro-situations (for example, transcripts of short conversations or videos of social interactions). Compared to the Chicago school of field research, ethnomethodology emphasizes method and claims that research data is as much the result of the method used as it is of the social life being studied.

Ethnomethodology suggests that social meaning is fragile and changeable, not fixed, stable, or enduring. The value is constantly created and recreated in the current process. For this reason, ethnomethodologists analyze language, including pauses and the context of speech. They believe that people "improve" their understanding of common sense using hidden, implied sociocultural rules, and that social interaction is a process of reality creation. People interpret everyday events using cultural

knowledge and "clues" from the social context. Ethnomethodologists study how ordinary people in everyday life (reality, environment) apply hidden rules to understand the meaning of social life (for example, to find out if someone was joking or not).

Ethnomethodologists examine in detail ordinary social interaction in order to establish rules for the construction of social reality and common sense, to understand how these rules are applied and how new ones are created. They argue, for example, that standardized tests and questionnaires measure a person's ability to understand hidden codes and apply common sense rather than evaluate objective facts.

Ethnomethodologists sometimes use "rule-breaking" experiments to demonstrate the simple unwritten rules by which people make sense of reality in everyday life. Researchers intentionally violate an implied social norm. "Breach" usually elicits a powerful social reaction that confirms the existence of the rule, demonstrates the fragility of social reality, shows that such hidden rules are important for the flow of ordinary life.

What is qualitative field research? A precise definition of field research is difficult to give because it is amorphous. It is more an *orientation* toward research than the application of a rigid set of techniques. The field researcher uses different methods to obtain information. Schatzman and Strauss give this definition: "The method of field research includes the application of any technique that may be useful to obtain the desired knowledge, to reflect on this information" [8]. The field researcher is a "methodological pragmatist" with resources; a talented individual, resourceful and able to think for himself while in the field.

Field studies are based on naturalism, which is also applied to the study of other phenomena (ocean, animals, plants). Naturalism involves the observation of ordinary events in a natural environment, and not in an environment invented and created by the researcher.

Naturalism and direct involvement mean that qualitative research is more flexible and less structured than quantitative research. This also means that project milestones cannot be completely predetermined, but they can serve as a guide or map.

There are some stages of field research but ethnographers rarely follow strictly them. In fact, flexibility is a key advantage of good field research, which allows the scientist to change direction and follow intuition. Experienced ethnographers - recognize, grasp opportunities, and adapt quickly to changing social situations. When starting work, the researcher realizes that he or she has little control over the data and almost no research focus. But once the researcher is integrated into the environment, he (she) focuses on certain problems and topics and controls the data.

Qualitative field research uses the ability to carefully look and listen, take notes and write regularly. Prior to entering the field, the beginner practices observing the usual details of the situation and writing them down. Attention to detail and memorization can improve with practice. Daily notes and a personal diary are also good practice for teaching field notes. Field research begins with a general theme rather than specific hypotheses. The researcher should not dwell on some initial, perhaps false concepts. He must be well prepared but open to new ideas. Preparing questions for field work takes time.

There are two types of deconcentration, dispersal of attention. The first is to look at a wide range of situations, people and social environments to get a feel for understanding the overall situation before deciding what to include and what to exclude from the focus of research interest. The second type is not to focus solely on the role of the researcher . social niche in order to survive in the field as much as possible without changing their main obligations as a researcher.

Another thing in preparing for the role of a field researcher is knowing yourself. Work in the field can have a strong impact on the identity of the researcher and his (her) worldview , transform the personality.

Environment or field " site " - the environment in which events occur or activities take place; it is a socially defined territory with movable boundaries. A social group can interact in multiple places. When choosing a site, the field researcher must consider three factors: richness of data, obscurity, suitability.

It is important for the researcher to establish relationships with *the " watchmen"*, i.e. people who have formal or informal power to control access to the playground . Field researchers can negotiate with them for access to it. Field entry strategy

Social relationships are negotiated and formed about the process of working in the field. Negotiations are carried out with each new member of the group until a stable relationship is developed, allowing access to the field and, after establishing trust, obtaining information and reducing hostility. It is assumed that the researcher will have to talk over and over again and explain what he is doing.

The researcher must decide to what extent he will talk about himself and about the study. Talking about his personal life, hobbies, interests, biography, he (she) can establish a trusting relationship and reveal information about himself. It must be remembered, however, that attention must be focused on events in the field.

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